

Factors Affecting Teacher Evaluation in Higher Education Institutions: A Citation Analysis

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Abstract

In higher education, teacher evaluation is conducted in every semester to know their teaching quality. Hence, the purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the factors that affect teacher evaluation practices at university level. This study comprises of two parts identification and analyzation. The main factors identified from literature (secondary data) are instructional and non-instructional and citation analysis was used as a research technique. Findings of this study show that in the category of non-instructional factors, instructor-related factor has more impact on teacher evaluation practice and administrative-related factor has less impact. Moreover, in the category of instructional factors, knowledge about the subject matter has more impact on teacher evaluation practice and teaching method has less impact. Further it can be done through primary collection of data for example, qualitative study to validate the past finding of the literature. The results of this study suggests that management should not make decisions regarding teacher's evaluation on the basis of instructional factors (filled evaluation forms) but non-instructional factors should also be considered

Keywords: *Teacher evaluation, higher education institutions, quality enhancement cell, quality education, citation analysis.*

1. Introduction

Teacher evaluation is a performance management tool in which teacher's quality of teaching is judged. According to Aslam (2013), as it is very complex process therefore, requires several interrelated activities which are connected to a certain purpose for instance; teaching quality. It has multiple valuable purposes for instance; managing teacher training, measuring teacher performance in order to make administrative decisions, providing effective classroom instruction to students, assisting students to select teachers and accountability of institutions (Bosetti, 1994). Researchers Tuytens & Devos (2011); Colby et al., (2002) have highlighted the significance of influential factors affecting the teacher evaluation like appropriate feedback, evaluation purpose and leadership attributes. Delvaux et al., (2013) stated that teacher evaluation has a huge impact on teacher's professional development and to emphasis on teacher's growth and development European countries and USA have executed evaluation system (Lejonberg et al., 2018). The way it is used differs from country to country in terms of its characteristics (Flores, 2012). According to Artés et al. (2017) in Spanish higher education, they judge quality of teachers by using students' perception on teachers' evaluation. Organization for economic cooperation and development (OECD) report declared that, in Australia and Mexico there is the presence of formative approach in teacher evaluation (Delvaux et al., 2013). In recent years, system of teacher evaluation on the basis of students' achievement has been expanded in many countries (Cuevas et al., 2018). This research stresses on the factors that have major impact on teacher evaluation practice.

2. Literature review

2.1 Performance measurement

Performance measurement, over the last 20 years, has gained increased importance in management, in general, and public management, in particular (Pollitt, 2006). Neely et al.(2005) defined performance measurement as: "A performance measurement system can be defined as the set of metrics used to quantify both the efficiency and effectiveness of actions". Employee appraisal, financial performance, balanced scorecard, and stakeholder methods (Jackson, 1995), are the topics of discussion within the literature of performance measurement. Teacher evaluation practice, however, is widely used system for performance

measurement (Crosby, 2005). Nowadays, performance measurement practices are employed globally in majority of universities (Kallio et al., 2017; Parker, 2012). According to, Radnor and Barnes (2007): “Performance measurement is quantifying, either quantitatively or qualitatively, the input, output or level of activity of an event or process”. Chen et al. (2009) stated that, performance measurement indicators are needed to stimulate quality of education in universities. The topic of performance measurement has been in debate in the public sector (Ter Bogt & Scapens, 2012). It consists of narrow as well as broad definitions; previously it emphasis on the qualitative and quantitative indicators to measure the results (Alach, 2017; Wang, 2002). However, now it does not only measures but manages and control by using performance information (Bisbe & Malagueño, 2012). Basically, measurement helps organizations to find their strengths and weaknesses and tells which initiatives to take in order to improve organizations performance (Amaratunga & Baldry, 2002).

2.2 Quality enhancement cells (qec)

QEC in Pakistan is formed by HEC to improve the quality of education in universities (Shah et al., 2017). The reason for the commencement of this cell is on self-assessment of quality parameters, such as: Programme Mission Objectives and outcomes Curriculum Design and Organization; Laboratories and Computing Facilities; Student Support and Guidance; Faculty; Process Control; Institutional Facilities and Institutional Support (Dilshad, 2010). Hina & Ajmal (2016) stated QEC’s are established to impose quality standards in universities of Pakistan. The authors suggests five basics for its framework which are: “Ownership of Quality and benchmarks, enhancing the quality of student learning outcomes, Involvement of all associated people, awareness of International points of view, Independence, and association”. QEC releases the information about teaching performance by collecting data from students and faculty members. However, it tells teachers about their respective results but do not give them proper suggestion on how to enhance their skills (Sahito & Vaisanen, 2017). One of the main purposes of QEC is to conduct teaching evaluation regularly by students, colleagues as per the guidelines of HEC (Batoool et al., 2010).

2.3 Teacher evaluation practice

Gilmour et al. (2018) stated that, teacher evaluation practice may enhance teaching qualities by assisting instructors to acquire effective skills and competencies. Tuytens & Devos (2018) argued that, evaluation of teachers can be useful if it is implemented through professional and experts. According to Ovando & Ramirez (2007) teacher evaluation is one of the most crucial function of human resources because in this management is in difficult situation to take into account both approaches for example, formative and summative. Delvaux et al. (2013) concluded that the most essential features of evaluation system are, valuable feedback, positive attitude of management and limited teaching experience. The term evaluation is used for evaluating performance as well for professional growth (Papay, 2012). It is argued by Abrami (2001) that teacher evaluations are the best way to measure the quality of teaching. However, there are certain disagreements by some scholars on its validity (Hornstein, 2017; Spooren et al., 2013). Teaching evaluation procedure can be further divided into: self-evaluation, peer evaluation, administrator evaluation and students’ evaluation of teacher and course (Ali & Hussain, 2018). Chen & Hoshower (2003) suggested students are the important factor in determining valuable information on teaching quality if evaluation forms are properly constructed. However, students are not in a position to judge all elements of teacher performance so, the questions like ‘how well teacher know the subject matter or is the course material up to date should not be asked from students.

2.4 Formative and summative evaluation

Basically, teacher evaluation has two main purposes termed as formative and summative evaluation. When teachers are provided with feedback to improve their teaching quality then it is said to be formative. Moreover, if such feedback is used to make administrative decisions then it is called summative (Murray, 1984). The difference between formative and summative evaluation was given in 1967 by Michael Scriven (Popham, 1988). Further author stated that the function of formative was to provide administrators

information about how to improve the programs. However, summative was used to know the value of the program which is completed. In universities, summative evaluation is commonly used to improve the teaching quality (Sozer et al., 2019). According to Peterson (2016) due to formative evaluation there is enhancement in student participation. Yao & Gardy (2005) concluded that teacher appreciate feedback from students, however they get anxiety regarding summative evaluation. In formative, employees are provided with information on how to improve their teaching ability (Hunter & Nielsen, 2013). It is challenging to balance and assimilate both the purposes of evaluation (Darling-Hammond, 2013). Formative evaluation is referred as improvement oriented approach (Angeles, 1988). Whereas, summative is referred as judgement oriented approach (Patton, 1996). Avalos & Assael (2006) declared that formative encourages professional growth of instructors, while summative makes them accountable for their actions. Both purpose of evaluation system are in controversy because formative demands teachers to be open, whereas in summative teachers cannot to open as it can have problem in their respective jobs (Delvaux et al., 2013).

2.5 Students perception towards teacher evaluation practice

Crumbley et al. (2001) studied the perception of students' evaluation towards the quality of teaching. From the students' point of view, Chen & Hoshower (2003) opine that quality teaching appears to be one of the most critical construct for their outcome. According to Hurney (2014), students' perception is influenced by teaching and contextual factors that are particular to each subject. When students' perceive that teacher evaluation result is used for improvements in teaching then they tend to give good scores, whereas, if they perceive that it is being used for tenure, promotion and salary decisions then they tend to give low scores (Worthington, 2002). Students want their views to be heard, so they fill the forms honestly. However, there are students who believe that it will not result in any change so, they just fill it quickly (Ahmadi et al., 2001). Spooren & Christiaens, 2017; Surratt & Desselle (2007) found that students believe that Teacher evaluation is important and applicable but they were sometimes irritated when it does not result in improve in teaching effectiveness. Eng et al. (2015) stated that there is element of biasness in students' perception, therefore they give good rating to those who are attractive to them (Felton et al., 2008). There is a criticism by Chen & Hoshower (2003) on teacher evaluation that students do not have appropriate knowledge about the teaching elements and subject matter. According to Ellis (2016) students' view on teaching approaches is the main quality indicator.

3. Objective

The objective of this is to identify and analyze factors that affect teacher evaluation practice.

4. Research methodology

Research approach for this study is quantitative and is purely based on secondary data. Furthermore, data is identified through literature and analyzed through citation analysis more specifically theoretical distribution of citation analysis. In theoretical distribution of citation, citation data of different research paper is analyzed and compared through the no. of times authors have quoted that particular paper in his work, which means higher the number of citation the higher the impact factor. So, in this study the factor having higher number of citations, will be the one who has more impact on the teacher evaluation practice and factor that has lower number of citations, will be the one who has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

5. Results and discussion

In this objective there are two parts, first part comprises of identification of factors and second part comprises of analyzation of factors that affecting teacher evaluation practice.

5.1 Identification of factors affecting teacher evaluation practice

So basically, the factors affecting teacher evaluation practice are categorized into two broad categories non-teaching related and teaching related factors.

Non-instructional related factors affecting teacher evaluation practice

Non- instructional factors is also termed as non-teaching factors which are further divided into instructor-related, student-related, course-related and administrative-related factors.

Instructor-related factors

Instructors Gender	Reference	Number of citations
	(Arvey, 1979)	Cited by 447
	(Dobbins et al., 1988)	Cited by 139
	(Mobley, 1982)	Cited by 214
	(Mitchell & Martin, 2018)	Cited by 68
	(Wagner et al., 2016)	Cited by 32
	(Boring, 2017)	Cited by 156
	(Mengel et al., 2018)	Cited by 80
Total		1136
Instructor's Age, Academic rank & Experience	References	Number of citations
Academic rank	(Pounder, 2007)	Cited by 186
	(Feldman, 1983)	Cited by 243
	(Lueck et al., 1993)	Cited by 29
	(Chye Koh & Meng Tan, 1997).	Cited by 67
	(Aleamoni, 1987).	Cited by 119
Total		763
Age	(Kinney & Smith, 1992)	Cited by 58
	(Clayson, 1999)	Cited by 111
Total		169
Experience	(Wachtel, 1998)	Cited by 685
	(Tang, 1997)	Cited by 116
Total		801
Instructors Personality	References	Number of citations
	(Feldman, 1986)	Cited by 272
	(Patrick, 2011)	Cited by 107
	(Clayson, 2013)	Cited by 20
	(Radmacher & Martin, 2001)	Cited by 127
	(Dev & Qayyum, 2017)	Cited by 1
	(Del Boca & Ashmore, 1980)	Cited by 33
Total		560
Halo Effect	References	Number of citations
	(Hugh Feeley, 2002)	Cited by 121
	(Clayson & Haley, 2011)	Cited by 72
	(Hammonds et al., 2017)	Cited by 20
Total		213
Instructor factor total		3550

Table 1: Instructor related factors

Student-related factors

Student's Gender	References	Number of citations
	(Peterson et al., 2008)	Cited by 31
	(Wilson & Doyle, 1976)	Cited by 35

	(Denson et al., 2010)	Cited by 146
	(Ali & Al Ajmi, 2013)	Cited by 10
	(Bachen et al., 1999)	Cited by 180
	(Badri et al., 2006)	Cited by 73
	(Walumbwa & Ojode, 2000)	Cited by 26
Total		501
Grade expectation, grade point average	References	Number of citations
	(Bejar & Doyle 1976)	Cited by 18
	(Hamilton, 1980)	Cited by 41
	(Ewing, 2012)	Cited by 67
	(Beran & Violato 2005)	Cited by 157
	(Olivares, 2001)	Cited by 56
	(Isely & Singh, 2005)	Cited by 212
	(Grimes et al., 2004)	Cited by 131
	(Crumbley et al., 2001)	Cited by 144
	(Ali & Al Ajmi, 2013)	Cited by 10
Total		836
Age, Motivation, Prior knowledge, and Emotion	References	Number of citations
Prior knowledge	(Driscoll & Goodwin, 1979)	Cited by 37
	(Ahmadi et al., 2001)	Cited by 78
	(Bassi et al., 2017)	Cited by 8
Total		123
Motivation	(Feistauer & Richter 2018)	Cited by 1
Age	(Ali & Al Ajmi, 2013)	Cited by 10
Emotion	(Grunenwald & Ackerman, 1986)	Cited by 38
Academic and maturity level	References	Number of citations
	(Pounder, 2007)	Cited by 186
	(Langbein, 1994)	Cited by 124
TOTAL		310

Cultural background	References	Number of citations
	(Davies et al., 2007)	Cited by 96
	(Ali & Al Ajmi, 2013)	Cited by 10
	(Burba et al., 2001)	Cited by 37
	(Al-Kuwaiti et al., 2014)	Cited by 5
Total		148
Student factor total		1967

Table 2: Student-related factors

Course related factors

Course type	Reference	Number of citations
	(Nargundkar et al., 2014)	Cited by 19
	(Basow, & Montgomery, 2005)	Cited by 52
	(Davies et al., 2007)	Cited by 96
	(Kulik & Kulik, 1974)	Cited by 130
	(Ting, 2000)	Cited by 93
Total		390
Course level	(Feldman, 2007)	Cited by 574
	(Langbein, 1994)	Cited by 194
	(Cashin, 1990)	Cited by 292
	(Pounder, 2007)	Cited by 186
	(Whitworth, 2002)	Cited by 85
	(Costin et al., 1971)	Cited by 772
Total		2103
Course content and Workload	Reference	Number of citations

Course content	(Pounder, 2008)	Cited by 78
Work load	(Ali & Al Ajmi, 2013)	Cited by 10
Total		88
Course factor total		2581

Table 3: Course-related factors

Administrative-related factors

Class size	References	Number of citations
	(Nargundkar & Shrikhande, 2014)	Cited by 19
	(Ahmadi et al., 2001)	Cited by 78
	(Gannaway et al., 2018)	Cited by 14
	(Bassi et al., 2017)	Cited by 8
	(Ali & Al Ajmi, 2013)	Cited by 10
Total		129
Timing of the day	References	Number of citations
	(Husbands & Fosh,1993)	Cited by 111
	(Chye Koh & Meng Tan,1997)	Cited by 67
	(DeBerg & Wilson, 1990)	Cited by 53
Total		231
Format of a class	References	Number of citations
	(Chye Koh & Meng Tan,1997)	Cited by 67
	(Nargundkar & Shrikhande 2014).	Cited by 19
	(Lei, 2010)	Cited by 55
Total		141
Administrative factors total		592

Table 4: Administrative-related factors

INSTRUCTIONAL RELATED FACTORS AFFECTING TEACHER EVALUATION PRACTICE

Instructional factors is also termed as teaching factors which are further divided into classroom management and behavior, teaching method, teacher's interest and knowledge about subject matter.

Instructional factors

Classroom management & Behavior	References	Number of citations
	(Abiola, 2013)	Cited by 10
	(Greimel-Fuhrmann & Geyer, 2003)	Cited by 145
	(Erdle & Murray 1986)	Cited by 64
	(Deepa & Seth, 2014)	Cited by 6
	(Oral, 2012)	Cited by 28
Total		247

Table 5: Classroom management & Behavior

Teaching method	References	Number of citations
	(Abiola, 2013)	Cited by 10
	(Afe & Egbochukwu 2001)	Cited by 3
Total		13

Table 6: Teaching method

Teacher's interest	References	Number of citations
	(Schiefele et al., 2013)	Cited by 48
Total		48

Table 7: Teacher's interest

Knowledge about subject matter	References	Number of citations
	(Schiefele & Schaffner 2015)	Cited by 108
	(Peterson et al., 2008)	Cited by 31
	(Greimel-Fuhrmann & Geyer, 2003).	Cited by 145
Total		284

Table 8: knowledge about subject matter

5.2 Analyzation of factors affecting teacher evaluation practice

In the second part of objective, factors affecting teacher evaluation practices are analyzed. As discussed above, there are two main factors **Non-Instructional** and **instructional** affecting teacher evaluation practice. Within non-Instructional factors there are sub-factors like instructor-related, student-related, course-related and administrative-related which are again divided into different variables and within instructional factors there are sub-factors like classroom management and behavior, teaching methods, teacher's interest and knowledge about subject matter.

1) Non-instructional factors

• Instructor-related factors

Instructor's gender, academic rank, age, experience, personality and halo affect variables comes under this factor. The number of citations each variable has are; gender (1136), academic rank (763), age (169), experience (801), personality (560) and halo effect (121).

• Student-related factors

Student's gender, grade expectation and grade point average, academic and maturity level, cultural background, prior knowledge, motivation, age, emotion variables comes under this factor. The number of citations each variable has are; gender (501), grade expectation and grade point average (836), academic and maturity level (310), cultural background (148), prior knowledge (123), motivation (1), age (10), emotion (38).

• Course-related factors

Course type, level, content and workload variables comes under this factor. The number of citations each variable has are; type (390), level (2103), content (78), workload (10).

• Administrative-related factors

Class size, timing of the day and format of the class variables comes under this factor. The number of citations each variable has is; class size (129), timing of the day (231), and format of the class (141).

In **instructor related factor**, instructor's gender variable has greater number of citations which is 1136, therefore, gender is the first variable affecting teacher evaluation practice. Second variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is experience which has 801 number of citations, third variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is academic rank which has 753 number of citations. Fourth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is personality which has 560 number of citations. Fifth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is instructor's age which has 169 number of citations. Sixth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is halo affect that has 121 number of citations.

So, according to citation analysis, instructor's gender variable is the one which has more impact on teacher evaluation practices and halo affect variable is the one which has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

In **student related factor** grade expectation and grade point average has greater number of citation which is 836, therefore grade expectation and grade point average is the first variable that affects teacher evaluation practice. Second variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is student's gender which has 501 number of citations. Third variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is academic and maturity level which has 310 number of citations. Fourth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is cultural background which has 148 number of citations. Fifth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is prior knowledge which has 123 number of citations. Sixth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is emotion which has 38 number of citations. Seventh variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is student's age which has 10 number of citations. Eighth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is motivation which has 1 number of citation.

So, according to citation analysis, grade expectation and grade point average variable has more impact on teacher evaluation practice and motivation variable has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

In **course related factor**, course level variable has greater number of citations which is 2103, therefore, course level is the first variable that affects teacher evaluation practice. Second variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is course type which has 390 number of citations. Third variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is content which has 78 number of citations. Fourth variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is workload which has 10 number of citations.

So, according to citation analysis, course level variable has more impact on teacher evaluation practice and workload variable has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

In **administrative related factor**, timing of the day variable has greater number of citations which is 231, therefore, timing of the day is the first variable that affects teacher evaluation practice. Second variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is format of a class which has 141 number of citations. Third variable that affects teacher evaluation practice is class size which has 129 number of citations.

So, according to citation analysis, timing of the day has more impact on teacher evaluation practice and class size has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

In the category of non-instructional factors, total number of citations in instructor-related factors as shown in table is 3550, student related factors is 1967, course related factors is 2581 and administrative related factors is 501. Hence, the factor instructor related has more impact on teacher evaluation practice. Second factor that has impact on teacher evaluation practice is course related factors. Third factor that has impact on teacher evaluation practice is student related factor. Fourth factor that has impact on teacher evaluation practice is administrative related factors. Therefore, administrative related factor has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

Figure 1: Non-instructional factors

2) Instructional factors

- **Classroom management and behavior**
The number of citations this factor has is (247).
- **Teaching method**
The number of citations this factor has is (13)
- **Teacher's interest**
The number of citations this factor has is (48)

- **Knowledge about subject matter**
The number of citations this factor has is (284).

In instructional factors, knowledge about subject matter has greater number of citations which is 284. Therefore, this factor has more impact on teacher evaluation practice.

Classroom management and behavior is the second factor that has impact on teacher evaluation practice having 247 number of citations. Teacher's interest is the third factor that has impact on teacher evaluation practice having 48 number of citations. Teaching method has 13 number of citations which means this factor has less impact on teacher evaluation practice.

Figure 2: Instructional factors

6. Conclusion

This study concludes that teacher evaluation practice is affected by numerous number of factors (instructional and non-instructional) which may cause problem in the validity of evaluation results. The results from citation analysis have shown that non-instructor factors affect teacher evaluation practice the most as the total number of citations of this main factor is 8,599 and the other main factor which is instructor factor affects less as the total number of citations is 592, which means the factors which are beyond the reach of teachers are having more impact.

This study contributes to the field of performance management more specifically in teacher evaluation literature. Mostly studies in this area are done on the basis of primary data (Bolliger et al., 2009; Patrick, 2011). However, this is done through citation analysis and have encountered both main factors (instructional and non-instructional).

6.1 Limitations and future research directions

This study is limited to secondary data analysis. Further it can be done through qualitative research by taking student/teacher as a sample.

6.2 Recommendation

This study will make higher education management understand that their main concern should be on non-instructional factors which might have negative impact on teacher's evaluation report, such factors are often neglected as they are invisible and beyond the control of a teacher. Furthermore, in teacher evaluation survey questions/statements are mainly based on instructional factors, they should also add few questions based on non-instructional factors in order to have a clear picture about evaluation results.

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